

Growth of Goods and Services Tax in India- A Study of Revenue Generated 2019-2023

Guguloth Chanti¹, Prof. B. Sudhakar Reddy²

Research Scholar, Department of Economics, Osmania University
Professor, Department of Economics, Osmania University

Abstract:

The concept of goods and services tax is one of the biggest revolutions in decades around the world. The GST is a biggest and substantial indirect tax reform since 1947. The main idea of GST is to replace the existing the taxes like value added tax, excise duty, service tax and sales tax. it will levied on the manufacture and sale and consumption of goods and services. The structure of the GST results in uniting the country economically. The main objective of this research is to investigate the revenue collection of goods and service tax month wise and its growth. The study used only secondary data. The study used to descriptive statistical tools and inferential statistical tools used. these results of study indicated that growth of the GST collection yearly.

Keywords: GST, Tax, Finance, Revenue

1. Introduction:

Taxation in India is retrenched form the period of Arthas astra. Present Indian tax system is based on this ancient tax system which is based on the social welfare. It is liability for every citizen of the country. These policies play an important role on the Indian economy. The Indian tax regime relied heavily on indirect taxes. Revenue from indirect taxes was the major source of tax revenue will tax reforms major cities. The concept of GST is one of the biggest revolutions in decades around the world. It is an indirect tax will subsume all the indirect taxes of central government and governments into to a unified tax. To remove tax cascading effect of the taxes, provide a common nationwide market for goods and services. GST will merge all indirect taxed under an umbrella. GST also beneficial for Consumers as there would be only one tax from the manufacturers and service providers to the consumer lending to transparency and efficiency. It will prevent leakages from the system and provide relief in terms of reduced tax burden on most of the commodities,

Received: 2 November 2023

Revised: 10 November 2023

Final Accepted 23 November 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10200656>

brings a new wave of economic reform in the country and help in improving tax governance in India. It is stated as, “As of 31st January, 2023, the number of companies registered under the Companies Act was 24, 61,937. Of these, 9, 04,723 companies were closed, 7,110 companies were under liquidation, 30,627 companies are in the process of striking-off from the register and 2,469 companies have so far obtained the “dormant” status according to Section 455 of the Companies Act, 2013. There are 15, 17,008 active companies, including 2,58,850 companies which were incorporated within the preceding eighteen months (not due for Annual Statutory Filings).”

2. Review of Literature:

Mohpatrar et al., (2018) in their study concluded that there is still a lack of awareness about the new tax reforms and also a deficiency of understanding and knowledge which can be attributed to various reasons like lack of government initiatives towards digitalization, awareness campaigns, lack of internet connectivity.

Pallavi Chaturvedi et al., (2017) GST will give a major boost to the make in India initiative of government of India by making goods and services produced in India competitive in the national as international market.

Dash (2017) Results indicated that the impact of GST we need to wait for the time and the governments needs to communicate more and more about systems. It could be a good way to reduce the black money and good effort by the government of the India after demonetization.

Garg (2014) in the article named Basic Concepts and Features of Good and Services Tax in India analyzed the impact and GST on Indian Tax scenario and concluded that it will strengthen out free market economy.

Kumar (2014) studied in the article Goods and Services Tax in India: A Way Forward background, silent features and concluded with the positive impact of GST on present complex tax structure and development of common national market

Bird (2012) summarizes in the article The GST/HST: Creating an integrated Sales Tax in a Federal Country the impact of GST will be on Canada.

3. Importance and significance of the study:

Received: 2 November 2023

Revised: 10 November 2023

Final Accepted 23 November 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10200656>

The historic GST has become a reality of the new tax system was launched at the functional hall of parliament on 1st July, 2017. It is a single indirect tax for the whole nation, one which will make India a unified common market. It is the survival of the Indian economy in the face of increasing international competition consequent to globalization and liberalization and GST have a positive impact on various sectors and industry for tax reform would be to address the problems of the current system. The impact of GST depends on the change in tax rates due to the introduction of the new tax regime. The GST law in India is a comprehensive, multi stage, destination-based tax that is levied on every value addition. It is levied by both the national and the state government.

4. Research Methodology:

The research study is based on the secondary data collected from various national and international articles, journals, working papers and various government ministries of India websites. The study is used descriptive statistical tools such as tables, charts, percentage analysis and interpretation of the data. Inferential statistical tools used such as paired t test and Anova. The study period covered implementation of GST 2019-23.

5. Objectives of the study:

1. To study the total revenue collection of Goods and Services Tax
2. To analyse the association between the collection of revenue collection of Goods and Services Tax

6. Testing of Hypothesis:

H₀1: There is no significant difference between the revenue collected year wise 2019-2023 India.

7. Data Analysis:

Tabel: -1

Total Revenue of Goods and Service Tax (GST) as on 30th March, 2023 (Rs. In Crores)

Year	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23
April	1,03,459.00	1,13,865.00	32,172.00	139708	1,67,540
May	94,016.00	1,00,289.00	62,151.00	97,821	1,40,885
June	95,610.00	99,939.00	90,917.00	92,800	1,44,616

July	96,483.00	1,02,083.00	87,422.00	1,16,393	1,48,995
August	93,960.00	98,202.00	86,449.00	1,12,020	1,43,612
September	94,442.00	91,916.00	95,480.00	1,17,010	1,47,686
October	1,00,710.00	95,379.00	1,05,155.00	1,30,127	1,51,718
November	97,637.00	1,03,491.00	1,04,963.00	1,31,526	1,45,867
December	94,726.00	1,03,184.00	1,15,174.00	1,29,780	1,49,507
January	1,02,503.00	1,10,818.00	1,19,875.00	1,40,986	1,57,554
February	97,247.00	1,05,361.00	1,13,143.00	1,33,026	1,49,577
March	1,06,577.00	97,590.00	1,23,902.00	1,42,095	1,60,122
Grant Total	11,77,370.00	12,22,117.00	11,36,803.00	14,83,292	18,07,679
MEAN	98,475.25	1,00,742.63	1,08,017.63	1,29,571.25	1,50,705.38
SD	4211.62	6177.24	26225.67	16456.37	7639.33
CV	4.28%	6.13%	24.28%	12.70%	5.07%

Source: Secondary data

Interpretation: As we can be seen from the average GST in the table above revenue increased by 1,00,742.63 from FY 2018-19 to FY2019-20, declined by 11,36,803.00 in the FY 2020-21 increased by 1483292 and 1807679 corers 2021-22 and 2022-23 compared to FY 2020-21. Comparing variance of revenue collection form the years 2018-19 to 2022-23 more consistency in the year 2018-19 and more variance in the year 2020-21.

The total collected revenue of GST in India trend line is shown in the Chart-1. The trend equation shows that the total collected revenue in crores $y = 17929x + 63017$ and $R^2 = 0.845$ (84.5%), shows that the fitted trend line is highly influencing.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the revenue collected year wise India.

Analysis of Variance statistical inference is applied to test the significant difference between the revenue collected in India form the period of 2018-19-2022-23.

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups (Years)	26470925940	4	6617731485	30.84174	0.0000	2.539689
Within Groups (Months)	11801385379	55	214570643.3			
Total	38272311319	59				

Source: Calculated from Secondary Data

Interpretation: It is observed from the data provided in the above table - 1.1 that revenue collected year wise form 2019-2023 F critical value is 2.539689 and p value is 0.0000. It concludes the p value is greater than 0.05 at 5% significant level, there is no significant difference between revenue collected year wise from 2019-2023.

8. Conclusion:

GST earnings have become the government's most important sources of increasing the country's revenue. The government uses this collection contributes to the nation's growth and development of social welfare programmes, sponsored schemes, subsidies to develop infrastructure, defense and son on. GST collection of data demonstrates the financial dynamism of a country. GST serves as an important indicator for the country's financial health. The GST revenue collection has been increasing or decreasing monthly. Overall, all the average GST revenue will explain why GST collections are considered a gauge for economic growth. It concludes that the GST earnings reduces the government's fiscal imbalance based on the number of factors. Larger GST revenue will indicate the good financial health of the nation and good reputation of the country. Raising

the GST collection indicates that consumers are increasingly purchasing products and using services that are GST applicable. This inevitably leads to the country's good gross domestic product.

References:

1. Bird, Richard M. (2012). The GST/HST: Creating an integrated Sales Tax in a Federal Country. The School of Public Policy, SPP Research Papers, 5(12), 1-38
2. Garg, Girish (2014). Basic Concepts and Features of Good and Services Tax in India. International Journal of scientific research and Management, 2(2), 542-549
3. Kumar, Nitin (2014). Goods and Services Tax in India: A Way Forward. Global Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 3(6), 216-225
4. Mohapatrar, Joliyap, Kamalvanshi, V and Kushwaha S (2018), perception of GST in Varanasi district of Uttar Pradesh, International journal of Agriculture Sciences, 7369-7371.
5. Pallavi Chaturvedi and surchi madan (2017) Goods and services tax, a game changer for Indian economy, Inspira, Journal of Commerce, Economics and Compur science, 3.5-3.8.
6. Desh a (2017) positive and negative impact of GST on Indian economy, international journal of management and applied science, 159-160
7. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goods_and_Services_Tax_\(India\)_Revenue_Statistics](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goods_and_Services_Tax_(India)_Revenue_Statistics)
8. https://www.taxmanagementindia.com/visitor/detail_article.asp?ArticleID=10750
9. <https://studycafe.in/more-than-12000-companies-registered-on-mca-in-jan-2023-199297.html#:text=There%20are%2015%2C%2017%2C008%20active,an%20Authorized%20capital%20of%20Rs.>
10. <https://taxguru.in/goods-and-service-tax/gst-collections-fy-2017-18-fy-2020-21.html>